

Transcriptomic profiling of healthy individual-derived LCL models revealed inter-individual variability towards-hypoxia-responsive pathways

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Supplementary data

Table S1: Summary of eight Prakriti-specific Lymphoblastoid cell lines (LCLs)

S.No.	Sample code	Prakriti	Gender	Age	LCL Code
1	TC0003	Pitta	Male	23	LCL V2b
2	TC0001	Kapha	Male	28	LCL V1b
3	TC0006	Vata	Male	28	LCL V3b
4	TC0004	Pitta	Male	37	LCL V2c
5	TC0002	Kapha	Male	29	LCL V1c
6	TC0007	Vata	Male	35	LCL V3c
7	TC0005	Vata	Male	28	LCL V3a

Hypoxia generation and time point validation

Fig S2(a)

Fig S2(b)

Fig S2(c)

Fig S2(d)

Fig S2: Time point validations using western blotting experiments at selected time points (0, 2, 4, 6, 12, 24, 48, and 72 hrs.). Figure S2(a), Kapha LCL (V1a), S2(b), Pitta LCL (V2c), S2(c), Vata LCL (V3c). S2(d) combined analysis of western data.

Fig S3: qRT-PCR data for hypoxia generation using 0.2% oxygen and time point validation at selected time points (2, 4, 6, 12, 24, 48, and 72 hrs.). HIF-1α and EGLN1 levels were checked using extreme Prakriti LCLs (one cell line from each Prakriti) treated for hypoxia time points in three biological replicates, N3, n3.

Baseline comparisons: Ingenuity Pathway Analysis of canonical pathways

Fig S4: Baseline comparisons (0 hrs.) of Kapha and Pitta using canonical pathways of IPA

Fig S5: Baseline comparisons (0 hrs.) of Kapha and Vata using canonical pathways of IPA

Fig S6: Baseline comparisons (0 hrs.) of Pitta and Vata using canonical pathways of IPA

GSEA-KEGG pathway analysis of pre-ranked gene list

Fig S7: KEGG pathway analysis using GSEA after 24 hrs. of hypoxia.

Fig S8: KEGG pathway analysis using GSEA after 48 hrs. of hypoxia.

Fig S9: Pooled data enrichment of canonical pathways after 24 hrs. using IPA

Fig S10: Pooled data enrichment of canonical pathways after 48 hrs. using IPA

Fig S11: Kapha data enrichment of canonical pathways after 24 hrs. using IPA

Fig S12: Kapha data enrichment of canonical pathways after 48 hrs. using IPA

Fig S13: Pitta data enrichment of canonical pathways after 24 hrs. using IPA

Fig S14: Pitta data enrichment of canonical pathways after 48 hrs. using IPA

Fig S15: Vata data enrichment of canonical pathways after 24 hrs. using IPA

Fig S16: Vata data enrichment of canonical pathways after 48 hrs. using IPA

Canonical pathways	Pooled		Kapha		Pitta		Vata	
	24	48	24	48	24	48	24	48
HIF-1a	↑	↑		↑	↑			
p53 signaling	↑						↑	
Glycolysis	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑			
Gluconeogenesis	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑			
Mitochondrial dysfunction		↑	↑				↑	
Oxidative phosphorylation	↓		↓					
Cholesterol biosynthesis					↓	↓		
Nucleotide biosynthesis	↓		↓				↓	↓
UPR		↑		↑				↑
GADD45 signaling		↑	↑	↑				
Granzyme A signaling	↑		↑				↑	
Interferon signaling				↓		↓		
Cyclin & Cell cycle regulation	↓			↓	↓	↓	↓	
Cell cycle checkpoint regulation	↑		↑				↑	
TGF-β	↑		↑					
VEGFA			↑					

Fig S17: Summary of IPA canonical pathways in pooled and in all comparisons after 24 and 48 hrs. of hypoxia

Fig S18: Gene enrichment biological processes using DEG after 24 hrs. with 1.5 fold (>1.5 and <-1.5 FC) using Gene profiler

Fig S19: Gene enrichment biological processes using DEG after 48 hrs. with 1.5 fold (>1.5 and <-1.5 FC) using Gene profiler

Fig S20: Cell proliferation after hypoxia treatment in Kapha, Pitta, and Vata using CFSE assay for selected time (24, 48, and 72 hrs.) points.